

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Deliverable D4.4 - Recommendations for strengthening climate co-production knowledge platforms exchange and for building long-term alliances

WP4 – Roadmap for policy transformational change

Version 0.0.1 | September 2025

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

Document History

Deliverable Title	Recommendations for strengthening climate co-production knowledge platforms exchange and for building long-term alliances
Brief Description	This report (D4.4) provides recommendations intended to improve a key, promising conduit of supporting resources and networks: climate adaptation platforms. The report focuses on key aspects that warrant attention to underpin effective platforms: adopting best practices to understand what users want and need; using taxonomies to support better connectivity between content, actors and platforms; tailoring content to meet the distinct needs of different types of users; building user engagement; sharing actionable knowledge, and measuring the impact of the platforms.
WP number	4
Lead Beneficiary	SEI Oxford
Author(s)	Rosie Witton, Sukaina Bharwani, Andreas Hoy, Karen Brandon
Contributors	Enora Bruley, Anna Scolobig, Lucía Moreno, Judith Bielsa, Marta Ellena
Deliverable Due Date	June 2025
Actual Delivery Date	September 2025
Nature of the Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public

Date	Ver.	Contributors	Comment
June 2025	V0	SEI Oxford, SEI Tallinn	Collecting information, conducting the webinar series, survey's, and interviews. Writing the first draft.
August 2025	V1	SEI Oxford, UNIGE	Reviewing the draft and completing the updates.
September 2025	V2	SEI Oxford, Ibercivis	Reviewing the draft and completing the updates.
September 2025	V3	SEI Oxford	Final version.

Table of Contents

Document History	2
Table of Contents	3
1. Executive Summary	5
Assets of platforms	6
Barriers confronting platforms	6
2. Introduction	7
2.1 Project Background	7
2.2 Aim	7
2.2 Structure of the Report	8
3. Conceptual Background	8
3.1 Climate Adaptation Platforms.....	8
3.2 Bridging the knowledge to action gap	9
3.3 Understanding good knowledge management	10
3.4 Co-production approach	11
3.5 Adaptation AGORA Digital Tools.....	11
3.5.1 Agora Community Hub.....	11
3.5.2 Digital Academies.....	12
3.6 Climate Adaptation Platforms Network.....	13
4. Methodology.....	14
4.1 Climate Adaptation Platform Survey	14
4.2 Climate Adaptation Platform Interviews	14
4.3 Adaptation Agora Pilot Interviews	15
5. Results	15
5.1 Connecting with platforms and users	17
5.2 Knowledge Management.....	17
5.2.1 Usability.....	17
5.2.2 Inclusivity	18
5.2.3 Trust	19

- 5.2.4 Transferability20
- 5.2.5 Connectivity21
- 5.2.6 FAIR Principles.....22
- 5.3 Measuring impact22
- 6. Recommendations26
 - 6.1 Knowledge Management.....26
 - 6.2 Build collaboration and boost interoperability among platforms26
 - 6.3 Adopt feasible measures to monitoring impact27
 - 6.4 Continue the Adaptation AGORA community of practice28
- 7. References.....29
- Annex 1. Survey Questions31
- Annex 2. Climate Adaptation Platform Interview Questions36
- Annex 3. Pilot Interview Questions.....38
- Annex 4. Platforms Interviewed39
- Annex 5. MEL Framework39
 - Table 1. Usability40
 - Table 2. Inclusivity41
 - Table 3. Trust.....42
 - Table 4. Place-based knowledge sharing.....43
 - Table 5. Connectivity and cross-fertilization between knowledge, users, and networks43
 - Table 6. FAIR Knowledge Management44

1. Executive Summary

As global temperatures continue to rise, the need is growing for understandable, science-informed, and up-to-date information about measures that can boost the resilience to the impacts of climate change at every level. Yet, even as the impacts of a changing climate are becoming more severe and more widespread, sophisticated sources of misinformation and disinformation are proliferating, making the search for accurate and authoritative sources of guidance more difficult and time consuming.

Against this backdrop, this report on “Recommendations for strengthening climate co-production knowledge platforms exchange and for building long-term alliances” by the **Adaptation AGORA project**¹ provides recommendations intended to improve a key, promising conduit of supporting resources and networks: climate adaptation platforms. These online knowledge hubs bring together relevant data, tools, research findings, case studies, learning opportunities, organizations, and people. They can connect those working in different places on similar issues to help their intended audiences learn from the experiences of one another. And, they can help uncover state-of-the-art knowledge to put limited resources to their most efficient and effective use. In short, these platforms are in a unique position to be a foundational source of information to drive needed change.

The recommendations in this report emerge from discussions within the Climate Adaptation Platform Network webinars held under the Adaptation AGORA project, as well as from findings of a survey with 16 Climate Adaptation Platforms (referred to as platforms) and individual interviews conducted with 10 knowledge managers and owners in Europe and four with Adaptation AGORA pilot regions, where citizens were engaged on climate adaptation solutions in four locations: Dresden, Germany; Malmö, Sweden; Rome, Italy; and Aragón, Spain. The focus of the survey and interviews was to enhance understanding of best practices for operating such platforms and for monitoring and evaluating (M&E) their impact. The survey was analysed using Microsoft Excel and the interviews were analysed using ATLAS.ti.

The report’s recommendations build on analysis of the survey and interviews, targeting key issues: knowledge management, the interoperability of and connections among platforms, and M&E of downstream impacts.

The report focuses on key aspects that warrant attention to underpin effective platforms:

- Adopting best practices to understand what users want and need
- Using taxonomies to support better connectivity between content, actors and platforms.
- Tailoring content to meet the distinct needs of different types of users

¹ Adaptation AGORA – A Gathering place to co-design and co-create Adaptation – is an EU Horizon project. Please visit the Adaptation AGORA project website here: <https://adaptationagora.eu/>

- Building user engagement
- Sharing actionable knowledge, and
- Measuring the impact of the platforms.

Assets of platforms

The interviews indicate that the platforms are considered useful and valuable for a variety of purposes: sharing knowledge, providing high-quality and trusted content, offering sources of inspiration and ideas, providing context-specific information, and supporting peer-to-peer learning and networking among users.

Those surveyed indicated that they believe increasing the interoperability of and connectivity between platforms is a key to making them more effective and impactful. They underscored that platforms should ensure a focus on increasing the usability, inclusivity, trust, connectivity, and transferability of information. They also underlined the importance of adhering to findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data principles, which provide a framework intended to enhance the discoverability of information by automated systems and thereby optimize the use of relevant information (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Barriers confronting platforms

The survey and interviews also revealed critical barriers that platforms confront and must address to achieve their aims:

Constraints posed by time-limited projects – Many platforms are project driven and, as a result, they are only available for a set period. This can lead to confusion and frustration among users and silos between platforms. Most of those interviewed expressed an interest in reducing this confusion and in building a dialogue among various platforms – both to learn from each other and to support the exchange of knowledge between platforms working at different levels (e.g., local or national platforms exchanging with regional or global platforms).

A lack of monitoring and evaluation to assess platforms' effectiveness – There is M&E needed to understand the degree of effectiveness of platforms and the impact the platforms have. Though platforms need to engage with their intended audiences to thoroughly assess what potential users want and whether active users' needs are met, many platforms instead rely on data analytic tools as a sole source of information. Other approaches – iterative feedback and co-design processes, such as surveys, trainings, and interviews – are not used as frequently, largely due to financial and capacity constraints.

Measuring the impact of a platform is important for a variety of purposes: to understand how to better attract potential users, maintain relevance with users, continuously improving and developing the platform as information and needs evolve, and report to funders and others on impact and outcomes.

2. Introduction

2.1 Project Background

This report (Deliverable 4.4 (D4.4)) is part of the EU-funded Horizon Europe project **Adaptation AGORA – A Gathering place to co-design and co-create Adaptation**². The project aims to support communities and regions participating in the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change³ by leveraging and advancing best practices to effectively engage citizens and stakeholders in adaptation decision-making and action.

Within the Adaptation AGORA project, Climate Adaptation Platforms (platforms) have been created to support citizen engagement, knowledge sharing, and discussions. To support this, Task 4.4 focused on building alliances with existing knowledge platforms to learn, share, and connect.

The key aim of this report is to share recommendations and best practices for platforms for understanding their users' needs, tailoring content to meet these needs, building user engagement, sharing actionable knowledge, and measuring the impact of this knowledge on climate adaptation action for and by citizens.

2.2 Aim

This report presents the results of a survey of platform owners and knowledge managers, and analysis of further in-depth interviews building on this survey and discussions with representatives from the projects pilot regions. This results in a comprehensive set of recommendations for platforms knowledge management good practice and a corresponding M&E framework to measure the impact of these activities.

² The AGORA project effectively engages and supports citizens and stakeholders in adaptation decision-making and action. Please visit the Adaptation AGORA project website here: <https://adaptationagora.eu/>

³ The EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change focuses on supporting EU regions, cities and local authorities to build resilience against the impacts of climate change. For further information please visit the website here: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en

Text box 1. Task 4.4 description

This task will convene online European climate adaptation knowledge platforms operating in the pilot regions to identify and act on opportunities for interoperability and complementarity with the Digital Agora. A series of bilateral and multilateral discussions with platform developers, practitioners and policy makers (e.g. starting from those involved in Task 4.1) will be used to create an alliance of online knowledge brokers serving the regions, and to understand and act on the added value of the Digital Agora to existing online governmental services supporting climate change adaptation. The latter includes strengthening collective efforts to share actionable knowledge for adaptation; exploring how the Digital Agora can be leveraged to connect local-level experiences with policy-making via the shared case studies and stories; creating beneficial connections between the platforms (e.g. via URLs and APIs) to enhance access to knowledge for citizens; to support the ongoing development of these governmental platforms through sharing best practices for citizen/user engagement; and, to ultimately build an alliance to increase the likelihood of long-term sustainability and social acceptability of citizen-led actions.

2.2 Structure of the Report

To start the report, the conceptual background of platforms and the Adaptation AGORA project digital tools are detailed. The report then includes more information on the methodology of gathering information through a survey and interviews, before moving into the recommendations on building platform connections and collaborations, knowledge management, and measuring the impact of platforms.

3. Conceptual Background

3.1 Climate Adaptation Platforms

Adaptation is defined as the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects, in order to moderate harm or exploit beneficial opportunities, in human systems. In natural systems, adaptation is the process of adjustment to actual climate and its effects; human intervention may facilitate adjustment to expected climate and its effects (IPCC AR6, 2023). As the focus and urgency for climate adaptation and enabling policies became an emerging topic, it became increasingly recognized that stakeholders, such as policymakers and decision-makers, need timely, relevant, and high-quality information to support the development and implementation of adaptation strategies and climate actions at both national and regional levels, through climate services, such as platforms (Panenko et al. 2021).

Climate Adaptation Platforms are web-based online spaces to help stakeholders address their climate adaptation needs. These platforms have different intended audiences, aims, scales, and

features which help support their intended users. Many countries in Europe have established or are in the process of developing platforms to provide accessible, evidence-based information and guidance to inform adaptation planning and implementation across different scales and regions such as German Climate Preparedness Portal (KLiVO-Portal), Adaptation Scotland, and the Spanish Climate Change Adaptation Platform (AdapteCCa). As more stakeholders and citizens learn and hear about climate change and its potential impacts, the more their requirement for knowledge and general understanding grows. Communication and engagement with stakeholders play a pivotal role and can be considered a powerful tool to enhance climate change adaptation and building resilience (Maibach et al. 2023), and platforms can, and have shown they can, support this.

3.2 Bridging the knowledge to action gap

Platforms can play a key role connecting and sharing information from one source to another. Platforms can be resource hubs of information, vital for helping users understand, learn, and connect with their topics of interest and at their level of interest (e.g. local, national, regional). When created, developed, and maintained effectively, platforms can act as critical infrastructures to deliver information to their intended audiences e.g. policy makers (Bharwani et al, 2025).

Many platforms can be supply or project driven, so are established and managed for a set period of time, or driven by donor and project requirements, with the assumption that by increasing the amount of knowledge available online, this will lead to evidence based decision making and understanding (Hammil et al., 2013, Barnard, 2011). However, the proliferation of portals and platforms sharing information online does not always result in a coordinated or systematic effort. This means knowledge can be fragmented and siloed leading to redundancy and/or replication, or it can mean that platforms become redundant or are abandoned after a project (when project funding finishes) (VanderMolen et al., 2019).

In addition, many platforms also face challenges to ensuring access to up-to-date material (Barrott et al. 2022). This can be a resource intensive activity to keep information on platforms relevant as there is a continuous production of new material. This amount of new material can also add to the overload of information and fragmentation of information between platforms. However, the rapid expansion of the number of platforms and amount of information available has not been met with the additional development of detailed and structured monitoring, evaluation, and learning frameworks (Swart et al., 2017).

While it can be understood that there are significant challenges to effective communication (Carone et al., 2025), platforms can play a key role in bridging this gap between knowledge and action through communication (Hammil et al, 2013). Platforms at all levels should engage in communications and exchanges with users and other platforms, to support sharing information at different levels, institutional networking, and existing governance structures. However, to understand if the roles platforms play are successfully having an impact, platforms need to measure their impacts and collaborate to identify good practices that can advance more informed and coordinated climate action (Bharwani et al., 2019).

3.3 Understanding good knowledge management

Platforms require clear and consistent knowledge management to be maintained. The work that is put into creating and maintaining platforms is referred to as knowledge management and can include the technical website development as well as content creation. This is usually done by knowledge managers or owners of the platform. Knowledge management highlights the potential to develop platforms that engage their intended audiences and bridge the gap between learning, theory, and practice (Street et al, 2022).

In this report knowledge management focusses on six key areas: usability, inclusivity, trust, transferability, connectivity, and FAIR principles (based on Bharwani et al. 2025):

- Usability - the usability of a platform focusses on ensuring the material on a platform is considered “usable” to the intended audience. Platforms can be considered “usable” through different methods including translation features, tailored content to the intended audiences, development of summaries or syntheses of information etc.
- Inclusivity – platforms can focus on their inclusivity by ensuring there is just and equitable sharing of knowledge. This includes highlighting and sharing different knowledge types e.g. local or indigenous knowledge, as well as from the user's perspective ensuring the platform is inclusive in its accessibility and options to share information.
- Trust – building trust on a platform is a vital area of knowledge management. Credibility and trust on a platform are complementary and clear, efficient, and up-to-date knowledge management, engagement with users, and co-production or co-creation activities that include the intended audience help to support building trust.
- Transferability – ensuring content available on platforms is easily transferable between different scales e.g. local, national, regional, as well as between different locations is vital for helping users to access and use the content practically. For example, transferable content could be created through the use of standardised templates.
- Connectivity – supporting engagement and connection between users and information (depending on the aims of the individual platform) can be undertaken through supporting the cross-fertilization of knowledge, users, networks and content.
- FAIR Principles – FAIR principles connect a lot of the knowledge management practices above but also focus on decolonising knowledge, ensuring platforms are accessible, contain relevant information, and develop capacity of users to use the platforms that best supports them.

As knowledge management consists of all activities that take place to ensure the platform has up-to-date content, runs smoothly, and engages users, this requires consistent capacity from knowledge managers and engagement from users. Activities also include raising awareness and engagement activities, whilst breaking silos between platforms and collaborating with others, so the responsibilities and requirements of knowledge management are extensive and can be

challenging due to funding limitations. Therefore, measuring the impact of platforms is vital for knowledge managers and owners.

Measuring the impact and progress of work is also key to understand and demonstrate the usefulness of the associated work and benefits it can bring. Measuring adaptation actions and knowledge exchange helps to understand the potential positive impacts, but also, the potential negative consequences (Magnan et al., 2016). Implementing monitoring and evaluation (M&E) frameworks to measure the impact of platforms, can also increase citizen and stakeholder awareness and interest in climate change adaptation efforts and highlight methods and activities to increase awareness and engagement with the platforms (Tompkins et al., 2018).

However, research shows that, overall, and across governance levels and sectors, climate change adaptation M&E systems are rarely programmed and implemented (Goonesekera and Olazabal, 2022). Consequently, there is a general lack of understanding, knowledge, and practice, and this includes for M&E of platforms. For platforms this is particularly hard, as measuring the impact of a platform must go beyond what are considered standard indicators such as indicators identified through website monitoring e.g. number of users, number of downloads etc.

As the number of platforms continues to grow it is key to identify the specific and evolving needs of the intended users. Depending on the objectives of the platform this could focus on a specific topic, location, or even intended audience. There are several frameworks available to assess the efficiency of research in informing policy and decision making (Panenko et al., 2021). However, there has been limited research into frameworks or best practices for platforms to measure their impact.

3.4 Co-production approach

Research suggests that the improvement of population resilience needs to come through effective and clear communication and needs to be participatory by engaging intended audiences to share their insights, what is useful to them, and how they can share and learn from the communication (Henriksen et al., 2018). This includes through platforms that have emerged as virtual places to share knowledge and experiences at different scales and on different topics, supporting knowledge exchange and learning. However, given the complexity and amount of new communication channels, it is crucial to identify the best way to engage relevant stakeholders (e.g. decision makers, citizens etc.), select the most suitable communication strategies and involve stakeholders to see how platforms can best communicate their information to build trust with platforms (Oliveira and Carvalho, 2023).

3.5 Adaptation AGORA Digital Tools

3.5.1 Agora Community Hub

The Agora Community Hub (ACH) is a co-designed platform that focuses on engaging citizens to share and discuss their climate adaptation projects and solutions. The Agora Community Hub aims to be a meeting point that enables and empowers citizens and local communities to network and

communicate, facilitating them to find peers and other communities from similar/other geographical or societal contexts to share their needs, knowledge, and experiences on climate adaptation issues and solutions.

By featuring individual and organisation profiles that facilitate the identification of relevant peers and potential collaborators, the Agora Community Hub provides accessible information and knowledge for local government, municipal services, and communities. Resources include local to municipal level tools and approaches, including case studies and stories sharing experience (enablers, barriers, lessons learned) on implementation. Built as part of the weADAPT climate adaptation platform, the ACH can access reliable and high-quality information and connect, the Agora Community Hub maximizes networking opportunities and links with other projects and initiatives on climate related issues.

Visit the Agora Community Hub: [Agora Community Hub - Agora](#)

3.5.2 Digital Academies

Through the Adaptation AGORA project, two digital academies have been created to support citizens and stakeholders to access open-source climate data for adaptation and tackle climate change disinformation.

To access and use climate data to monitor climate risks

The digital academy to access and use Climate Data and monitor Climate Risks is designed to make scientific and high-quality information available to citizens and stakeholders thus helping them better understand complex data sets and how to use them. In doing so, Climate Data can be used as the knowledge basis for decision making processes that can be supported by Climate Data as well as ongoing Climate-Risk monitoring processes. Adaptation AGORA's Climate Databases can contribute to increasing community awareness on climate-related and adaptation issues.

The digital academy not only provides access to data but also support users with guidelines on how to read, interpret and effectively use the information, it can empower stakeholders and increase sustainable development. As a living tool, it will allow citizens to signal out existing initiatives and their impact at local and European levels, to inspire other communities on how to tackle climate-related risks.

Visit the digital academy to access and use climate data and monitor climate risks: [Agora – Climate Data Risks & Tools Academy](#).

Climate Change Disinformation

The digital academy against Climate Change Disinformation aims to equip citizens and stakeholders with reliable climate change information and fact-checked data from credible sources on climate change. Based on scientific evidence, it identifies and addresses fake news on this topic and provides

citizens with the tools to tackle misinformation. It is an interactive training space, developed using educational-based software. The digital academy provides comprehensive resources and educational materials, empowering users to discern accurate information, understand the impact of disinformation, and engage in informed discussions. Regular updates ensure content reflects the latest scientific findings and fact-checking efforts, promoting environmental literacy and evidence-based decision-making in addressing climate change challenges. Resources available include:

- Definitions and key facts regarding each issue derived from climate change and its inherent risks
- Trustworthy information, such as articles and scientific publications
- Fact-checks that debunk climate change disinformation
- Relevant resources, such as media literacy material
- Bi-annual reports on the state of disinformation around climate change. The reports will include a summary of the most viral disinformation narratives, accompanied by related fact-checks, and additional scientific information to support them.

Visit the digital academy on Climate Change Disinformation: [Home - Adaptation AGORA](#)

3.6 Climate Adaptation Platforms Network

Ensuring that platforms are able and encouraged to exchange and share knowledge, to build collaborations and discuss challenges and best practices, is a key part of T4.4. The network of platforms was created, based on the style of a community of practice and built on work and connections previously identified through the [KE4CAP project](#).

The main activity conducted through this network was a webinar series for platform owners and managers. The webinars provided a closed and safe environment to encourage participants to openly exchange knowledge, share and discuss their challenges, and learn from others who are working on similar topics.

The [first climate adaptation network webinar](#) under the Adaptation AGORA project, conducted in February 2024 was co-organised by the Adaptation AGORA project, three EU Horizon projects (MAGICA, MAIA, and SD-WISHEES), and the EU Mission Adaptation Community of Practice. The organisers identified potential advantages from working together, engaging in dialogue with national and regional/transnational platforms. The prime aim of the webinar was to inform participants about the projects, their respective intentions, and seeking platforms views as to how best engage them as part of the respective EC-funded projects and the Mission's Community of Practice. An open discussion engaged participants to share their perspectives and insights on building synergies and collaborations between EU projects and platforms, and critical next steps to achieve this.

There was a well expressed need to continue these types of dialogues within the right types of forums and engaging a broader community. Especially regarding discussions around best practices and challenges. There were the interest and potential of such, including more focused dialogues on particular projects, outcomes, or issues. But also to use this network and community to get engaged on these projects and platforms.

Following the initial webinar and discussion, key topic areas of interest were identified and webinars included:

- Connecting knowledge to policy and practice
- Going beyond standard analytics: measuring the impact of platforms
- Nature-based solutions for climate resilient cities: digital tools for decision-makers

The network is aiming to move forwards through the creation of a new Mission Community of Practice Thematic Working Group.

4. Methodology

This section details the process of gathering information on platforms via a survey and interviews with platform knowledge managers and owners and pilot region representatives.

4.1 Climate Adaptation Platform Survey

A platform survey was conducted in April 2025 and shared with the specific audience of platform owners and managers who had engaged with the webinar series or were contacts working in this space e.g. from the project's pilot regions, and 16 survey responses were collected.

The survey focused on identifying knowledge management activities that strengthen knowledge exchange, peer-to-peer learning and building long-term alliances. Topics and questions focussed on key aims, the intended audience, barriers and enablers to achieving the platforms objectives, knowledge management and knowledge exchange activities and whether these activities are monitored to evaluate what impact they are achieving. The survey was shared with platform owners and knowledge managers who had engaged with the Climate Adaptation Platform Network or were contacts of SEI who worked on platforms. This targeted approach allowed the survey to be completed in-detail by those who have first-hand experience with platforms and provide insights on the platform's knowledge management practices, development, and impact. The survey was analysed using Microsoft Excel and to access the full survey questions, please see Annex 1.

4.2 Climate Adaptation Platform Interviews

Interviews were conducted with specific platforms, some of which did or did not complete the survey. Platforms were selected for interview based on their experience and knowledge with monitoring the impacts of their platforms, their expertise in knowledge management and their general availability.

Interviews were conducted with 10 knowledge managers and owners of platforms working at a global and national level but with a focus in Europe (see Annex 4) and analysed using ATLAS.ti. Building on the impact pathways to actionable information identified for the weADAPT climate change adaptation platform (Bharwani et al., 2025), the interviews focused on coordination, learning and/or collaboration between users, engagement with intended audiences, different types of knowledge management activity, and the degree to which evaluating the impact of their platforms had been done. Interviews also discussed the degree of collaboration between platforms, the perceived usefulness of platforms and the potential impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on knowledge management and platforms in general. Insights from the interviews result in recommendations for high-impact knowledge management activities (Section 5.3) and a customizable M&E framework for platforms to measure their impact (Section 5.4).

4.3 Adaptation Agora Pilot Interviews

Four pilot studies were conducted under the Adaptation Agora project. The four pilot studies were focused in:

- Dresden, Germany – focusing on heavy rain, flooding, and heat waves.
- Malmö, Sweden – focusing on heatwaves.
- Rome, Italy – focusing broadly on all climate hazards relevant to sectoral impacts, as outlined in the city’s adaptation strategy.
- Aragón, Spain – focusing on heatwaves and flooding.

Four members of the Adaptation Agora project or key contacts within the pilot studies were interviewed (one per pilot study) to determine their input and feedback on platforms, concerns they have, what works well, and if they use platforms regularly. Interviews were analysed using ATLAS.ti.

5. Results

This section focuses on the results of the survey and interviews conducted with platforms knowledge managers/owners in March-August 2025. Results have been extracted and focus on connecting with platforms and users, as well as knowledge management practices, and measuring the impact of platforms.

It is clear from the interviews that platforms are considered useful and valuable for knowledge management such as knowledge sharing, high quality and trusted content, and content that provides inspiration and ideas. Platforms were further highlighted as useful spaces to provide context specific information, peer-to-peer learning, and support networking between users.

However, the survey and interviews indicated that platforms face barriers to achieving their aims and objectives. According to the survey conducted, platforms highlight that funding and keeping content up to date on the platforms were among the most cited challenges. This is supported by

the interviews conducted which indicate that some of the main challenges faced by platforms are the lack of funding and consequent person/time resources available to work on the platforms and therefore keep the content up-to-date.

Figure 1. Barriers to platforms achieving their objective. Source: Survey (n=16), April 2025.

Despite the barriers, the survey identified key methods platforms have used to achieve their aims and objectives. The key enabler identified was networks and connections. This referred to building networks and connections with other platforms, but also with the users of the platform. Through the interviews, platforms further indicated that there should be increased coordination and collaboration between platforms to support exchange of knowledge, challenges, and best practices between platform managers and owners. By engaging with platforms already available it also helps to support the awareness of different platforms, build on what content already exists, and reduce duplication of effort and material.

Figure 2. Enablers to platforms achieving their objective. Source: Survey (n=16), April, 2025.

5.1 Connecting with platforms and users

As highlighted in section 3.2, platforms can play a vital role in bridging the knowledge to action gap. In particular, during the interviews, platforms connecting to each other was a recurring discussion topic. As many platforms are funded through project-based funding they can only plan operations based on the duration of that funding, and knowledge managers reported this can lead to frustration and confusion for users and silos between platforms. However, most platforms interviewed expressed an interest to reduce this confusion for platform users and build a dialogue between platforms to learn from each other but also to support the exchange of knowledge between platforms working at different levels e.g. local or national platforms exchanging with regional or global platforms. Platforms including Climate-ADAPT and Adaptation at Altitude reportedly connect with other platforms by sharing links to the other platforms to help guide users and share information between platforms. Another way for platforms to be connected is by using microsites. weDAPT allows [microsites](#) to be built as separate platforms but connected with the weADAPT platform, therefore building on an existing community of research, policy, and practice so information can be shared easily between the platforms.

Henriksen et al. 2018 and Thomas et al. 2021 suggests that the improvement of population resilience needs to come through effective and clear communication and needs to be participatory. Some platforms, such as weADAPT, where relevant to their objective, support user engagement through user profiles and networking features on their platforms to help build knowledge exchange, discussions spaces, and connection between users. However, within the interviews it was noted that building engagement between platforms and users can be challenging and is often limited, depending on the aim of the platform and capacity and resources available.

5.2 Knowledge Management

Platforms contain and share different types of information for their intended audiences. The work that is put into creating and maintaining platforms is referred to as knowledge management and can include the technical website development as well as content creation. In this section knowledge management focusses on five key areas: usability, inclusivity, transferability, connectivity, and FAIR principles.

5.2.1 Usability

Knowledge managers interviewed identified that to successfully reach their intended audiences, having a platform and content that was considered 'usable' as opposed to just useful (Lemos et al., 2012) is critical. A lot of elements or features go into making a platform usable, and whilst there are some common methods used to reach audiences, some specific features can vary between platforms.

For example, to increase the usability of weADAPT the platform tailors' content to different audiences e.g. introduction articles to a topic, categorising and filtering content, and having clickable links within content all help create content that is clear and easy to navigate. For example, some knowledge managers and the Adaptation Agora pilot study interviews highlighted that learning studies can be more important and more useful than case studies in terms of content type. Learning studies provide peer-to-peer learning that can be more powerful than learning from research which is often not translated for practitioners or decision-makers at different scales. By ensuring content is tailored to different audiences, this can support learning, understanding, and building resilience of the intended audience e.g. communities.

Language was a key factor of usability that was mentioned by most platforms interviewed including weADAPT and MIP4Adapt. Platforms that work at a regional level indicated they had information available in multiple languages, either through an automatic translation feature or by having content translated into selected EU languages. Some platforms that focussed on a national level also indicated they had translation features available or were in the process of translating some key resources from their national language/s to include English e.g. Climate Adaptation Platform Netherlands. All knowledge managers interviewed agreed that an important way to increase the usability of a platform is to ensure that platforms used terms that were not jargon and were clear for the audience to understand.

Knowledge managers indicated that for the users of the platform, the location of use can be monitored through website analytics e.g. Google Analytics. Website analytics also allows knowledge managers to see what content is being accessed and in what languages, to help identify the reach of the resources.

Knowledge managers highlighted during the interviews that it is important to gather feedback and input on the usability of the platform to understand the user's perspective, to improve the platform and users experiences, but also to gather information to report to funders. Ensuring the platforms are usable and used by their intended audience is important to report to funders and show that platforms are having the intended impact, users are engaging with the platforms, and that the platforms should continue to be funded. To increase the usability of the platforms and content, feedback can be collected on a regular basis through feedback emails, newsletters, surveys, in-person discussions and interviews etc. And some knowledge managers highlighted that they offer trainings for users on how to best use the platforms and access or share the information available on it or trainings to trainers to encourage peer-to-peer learning. However, measuring the impact of the trainings and peer-to-peer learning spaces was often reported as challenging or not undertaken, likely due to resource and financial constraints.

5.2.2 Inclusivity

Just and equitable knowledge sharing of different and multiple knowledge types supports build the inclusivity and cross-community learning of a platform (Bharwani et al., 2025). A lot of knowledge

managers surveyed and interviewed highlighted, they were trying to be inclusive on their platforms by targeting their specific audiences at different levels, encouraging capacity building, having content in multiple languages, and supporting diversity of authors, users, and organisations on the platform. However, some of these indicators are hard to collect information on, measure, and therefore hard to monitor the specific impact the platform is having.

Some platforms such as weADAPT went further and measured the number of people who were contributing content who were youth or from the Global South as well as how many organisations were registered and if they were community-based organisations. Some platforms, depending on the type of content they had available, have added content types that aren't solely academic or focused on published papers, to help support the diversity of information shared on the platform, such as blogs and information from local projects and communities, which may not be available in the format of a published paper.

Another method used to support inclusivity on the platform is by offering trainings for users to learn about the platform, how to use and navigate it, and how to contribute or get involved. This supports those who might not be aware or have confidence using the platform to learn, access, and share information.

Technical inclusivity on the platform was also highlighted as a key factor. For example, ensuring the colours used on the platform meet required guidance, text is large enough for the average user to read on different screens, and the platforms have features to reduce image size in case of limited internet access such as on weADAPT.

5.2.3 Trust

Building trust in a platform, the content on the platform, and with the knowledge managers is an important part of encouraging people to use platforms. During the interviews, knowledge managers highlighted the importance of building trust, recognising how this can sometimes be challenging. One of the main methods used to build trust with users was by co-designing the platforms and then gathering iterative feedback from users on the platform and implementing their suggestions (see [Adaptation Agora D3.1](#)). This continued engagement at different levels of types of users is important to gather perspectives and feedback through informal feedback e.g. contact pages or discussions, as well as through surveys and networks.

The type of content available also supports building trust with users on the platform. Firstly, by having content available in the users first language or multiple languages (that can then be translated into English, rather than having the content in English and translating it into their first language). Secondly, the type of content available on the platform can support trust. For example, if knowledge is shared top-down, a lot of types of users may be missed. Whereas if there is a variety of content on the platform that has been quality checked and reviewed, this can support users in building trust.

Supporting networking and learning on a platform can build trust with users through trainings of how to use the platform, but also through webinars on topic areas of interest, and providing spaces to network. This helps users engage with the platform owners and managers and continued engagement will build trust with users over time, as well as discuss and connect with other users and learn from their experiences. These engagements can be very transformative for building trust with the users, peer-to-peer learning, and fostering connections.

It was highlighted by Climate Adaptation Platform Netherlands that trust is built with users by the knowledge manager engaging with users. Having a contact available to support and answer questions that users have is beneficial, and knowledge managers and owners can help develop capacity of future and other knowledge managers and owners.

However, there can be challenges as a lot of platforms are linked to projects and consequently funding, so the longevity of the platform is brought into question, which negatively impacts trust with users.

Measuring the amount of trust a user has in a platform is a challenge. Trust is a unique and individual concept to each user. However, the elements identified to build or encourage trust in a platform can be measured, such as the use of content in multiple languages, the diversity of content, if content has been through a quality review process, the level of engagement on the platform, and if the platform itself was co-developed or receives and implements feedback from users.

5.2.4 Transferability

Transferability of knowledge between users, scales, and platforms is important to support platforms with meeting their objectives. Platforms can support in transferring knowledge between users through networks and encouraging peer-to-peer learning, and building connections, as well as through standardised templates on a platform that ensure the information available is shared in the same format for ease of understanding. In particular, standardised templates support cross learning at different scales such as national to regional.

Transferability also applies to information shared between platforms. Some platforms share content through website application programming interfaces (APIs), and to do this, content must be shared in a similar format or template to be compatible between platforms.

In order to measure the transferability of information, it is first important to measure the amount of content available on each of the platforms. Platforms interviewed indicated that they try to encourage transferability between content at different scales or regions, but many were not actively doing this and therefore were not actively measuring the impact of this. A few platforms reportedly used APIs to share content between platforms, however, these platforms indicated that unless they were connected as microsites e.g. weADAPT then if content was shared between platforms to increase awareness and engagement with the content, then the impact of the content was measured per platform.

5.2.5 Connectivity

Building connections between the platform, users, and knowledge can be used to enhance the user friendliness of a platform (accessibility and usability), as well as the transferability of information. Platforms reportedly build connectivity between users through technical features such as notification systems to alert users to new or relevant content and events, as well as engagement through networks or peer-to-peer learning spaces where users can share and exchange knowledge, challenges, and good practices. However, knowledge managers noted in the interviews that building engagement on these networks can be challenging as user engagement can be limited. Linked to this, in order to build user engagement this requires consistent and continuous funding and capacity which platforms stated in the interviews could be limiting.

To build user engagement, the usability, and the connectivity on a platform, content within a platform can be connected to other related content, to enhance user navigation, help users see the content available on a platform, and guide users to read further into the topic and content. Content on a platform can be connected through tagging systems that platforms use. Most platforms interviewed reported having some type of tagging system for content, that enhanced content discoverability and supported users to read further, however the tagging systems were reportedly not standardised within or between platforms. The technical aspect of tagging systems allows content to sit within multiple spaces on a platform and where tagging systems appear on content, e.g. adding a tag to a piece of content, platforms often reported that this allows users to click the tag and all content with that tag can then be accessed.

Connectivity between platforms was highlighted as an important issue within the interviews, with most platform managers/owners stating that better coordination and collaboration between platforms would be beneficial for them and for users. Some platforms share content through technical (application programming) interfaces (APIs), to ensure the content and knowledge on the platforms gains visibility and engagement from multiple audiences, however this also decreases the workload on knowledge managers and supports their work with limited funding and resources.

However, some platforms allowed users who created profiles to “follow” and “message” other users to encourage collaborations, as well as open discussion spaces where users could ask or answer questions and engage in conversations with peers. The impact of these can be monitored through proxy indicators of activity.

Consistent and standardised tagging on content can support monitoring processes by enabling and enhancing connections between content, identifying key areas of interest and knowledge trends, and identifying knowledge gaps.

Whilst some platforms did not have a focus or objective on fostering connections and collaborations between users or organisations, those that did, encourage connections between users through discussion spaces, categorising content into themes, adding notifications, and tagging content. The

impact of this is particularly challenging to monitor unless through surveys or virtual/face-to-face discussions.

In order to gather feedback on the platform from users, in addition to analytics, some platforms interviewed indicated that they got most feedback and input through informal methods, such as informal discussions or emails to the generic contact email for the platform. Some platforms requested more in-detail feedback on the platform through surveys, which was done on a more irregular basis e.g. 1-2 years.

5.2.6 FAIR Principles

Aligning the knowledge management activities above with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles is essential to having an effective and usable platform. Whilst the FAIR principles were not addressed directly during the interviews, many of the features mentioned by each platform can be connected to these principles, such as platforms that mentioned dealing with low connectivity as an accessibility issue. Platforms also increase accessibility by sharing content and engaging with audiences through different communication methods, such as disseminating information and content via newsletters and social media, as well as encouraging peer-to-peer dissemination. By using these channels, it supports the accessibility of the platform and its content.

Features to support the FAIR principles such as low-bandwidth versions of the platforms, tagging and categorising content, language translation features, downloadable documents, and short user journeys through a platform are all important aspects of the FAIR principles.

Another method to support FAIR principles is to ensure platforms are leveraging new technologies, such as AI. Climate-ADAPT have recently introduced their AI assistant, and many other platforms noted they were looking into how to leverage AI to support capacity, user engagement, and connectivity between platforms, with many platforms noting this was still being investigated as there were concerns and uncertainty about negative implications, so platforms were moving forwards with caution.

5.3 Measuring impact

Overall, there is limited M&E or measurement of the impact of platforms. Some platforms, such as weADAPT and the KLIVO-Portal have completed evaluations of the platforms looking at indicators on website development, user needs, and awareness of the platforms (Adam and Weiss, 2025, Bharwani et al, 2025); however the number of platforms that have reportedly been able to undertake such evaluations is small and primarily limited to those that are long-lived. The survey identified that the majority of platforms said measuring the impact of their platform was helpful, as seen in Figure 3. As shown in Figure 4, some platforms surveyed measured the impact of their platform by measuring the analytics of the platform e.g. the number of visitors, the number of times a piece of content was accessed or downloaded etc. This information is often used for reporting

purposes and indicators are created from this information to show the progress of a platform towards meeting its aims. However, this style of analytics can be limited and only focusses on the access to the platform, rather than the extent that the platform is meeting the needs of users. During the survey and interviews, platforms highlighted their methods of evaluating impact and only a handful of platforms took this further than monitoring the analytics and did not have a Theory of Change (a framework to measure impact/change), as they only focused on incremental improvements, such as Adaptecca. Most platforms interviewed stated that upon gathering feedback from analytics, user surveys or interviews, feedback provided was taken into account and actioned to support addressing the user needs on the platforms. Some platforms such as the KLIVO-Portal, do go one step further to gather information about the impact of the platform and have conducted an in-detail assessment of the platforms impact through surveys and interviews. In addition, one of the main ways platforms reported receiving feedback was through face to face, or more informal, discussions with platform users. Feedback and inputs provided from surveys and interviews with the platform users generally provide more in-detail information. It is also important to note that some platforms that don't specifically evaluate the platform's impact, they are monitoring the progress towards meeting their programme aims, which includes online content and in-person events where the platform is mentioned. This is a form of M&E for the platform that can be connected to the programmes Theory of Change and indicators, such as with the Adaptation Scotland platform.

However, there is still a gap when it comes to measuring the impact of platforms. Conducting an evaluation based on analytics of the platforms provides a good overview of information but platforms need to invest time and capacity in further M&E of the platforms by engaging with their users and identifying user needs.

Figure 3. Platforms that find understanding their impact useful. Source: Survey (n=16), April, 2025.

Figure 4. How platforms measure impact. Source: Survey (n=16), April, 2025.

weADAPT’s monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL) framework (Bharwani et al., 2025) has been adapted using insights from interviews with platforms knowledge managers and pilot regions (Section 5). It is also informed by experiences from Climate-ADAPT (following their updated [strategy](#)) and KLiVO-Portal (Adam and Weiss, 2025) evaluations. This version of the weADAPT MEL framework, customized for European national climate adaptation platforms enables it to be easily operationalized. It can include indicators that track contribution to the country’s National Adaptation Plan (NAP) or equivalent, EU-wide targets based on the EU Adaptation Strategy, and the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. Adherence to a common M&E approach enhances the potential better tracking of adaptation progress as well as vertical integration of content from national and sub-national platforms within global platforms and vice-versa to accelerate learning about good practice at the local level, reducing content redundancy and replication.

A standardized approach to describing content using a common vocabulary or taxonomy (rarely mentioned by knowledge managers) supports robust, standardized monitoring and comparability across platforms of adaptation measures, successes and challenges whilst increasing the potential for sharing content. MEL approaches can include tracking many elements. Using the weADAPT framework, six domains are recommended for monitoring platform effectiveness (usability, inclusivity, trust, connectivity, place-based and FAIR), and within these priority indicators mentioned by participants in the study or through the literature review are highlighted (Figure 5). Other more detailed indicators are included in Annex 5, such as, the uptake of nationally produced resources related to EU adaptation priorities (e.g., nature-based solutions, climate-resilient infrastructure), including cross-border uptake, how many times national platform outputs are cited in other national adaptation portals, other networks, on Climate-ADAPT or in European Commission reports, and how many national resources align with EU priority sectoral policies (e.g., agriculture, energy, health, water) or EU social inclusion priorities (e.g., rural communities, youth networks).

The following example summary can be used as a snapshot of progress at quarterly intervals and shared with relevant stakeholders and funders (e.g. Figure 5). More detailed information can be collated through the MEL framework (Annex 5). Some indicators can be gathered through regular software analytics, such as Google or social media analytics data. Others require early integration into platform design for curated analytics, including ‘proxy’ indicators that are hard to measure directly and may need indirect measurement and manual effort. Additionally, if standardized tags using taxonomies are applied, it becomes easier to collect this data in an automated way. Certain indicators are best monitored through mapping and graph visualizations.

Theme	Indicator	Current Value	Target	Trend
1. Usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of content formats accessed Top 5 EU national languages content is translated to Policy uptake - EU and national policy document citations 	x%	x%	↑ improving
2. Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> % content from less-represented, -resourced or climate-vulnerable regions 	x%	x%	→ stable
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation of groups relevant to EU social inclusion priorities (e.g., rural communities, youth networks) 			↓ declining
3. Trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Newsletter forwarding rate, referrals and visitor return rates Use of feedback forms 	x%	x%	↑ improving
4. Connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Referrals from other national adaptation portals or networks Number of communities of practice around a topic or issue formed through the platform Engagement via online contributions or attendance rate at core events Transboundary, cross-national and regional collaborations initiated Cross-border uptake of nationally produced resources Cooperation with neighbouring countries on adaptation (joint workshops, shared datasets) 	x%	x%	↑ improving
5. Place-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National and regional case studies covering key adaptation options of critical importance to intended users, EU adaptation priorities and sectoral policies 	x%	x%	→ stable
6. FAIR Knowledge Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> % new content with machine-readable metadata 	x%	x%	→ stable
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> % new content using a standardized taxonomy 	x%	x%	↑ improving

Table 1: Monitoring key platform domains, showing trends in the current quarter versus the previous quarter.

6. Recommendations

The report makes the following recommendations aimed at improving the reach and utility of the platforms, and at better understanding the ways in which they impact decision-making:

6.1 Knowledge Management

Managers should:

- Make information available in multiple languages (in-line with the platforms intended users).
- Provide networking features such as communities of practice.
- Take advantage of peer-to-peer learning.
- Include different types of knowledge from different sources.
- Provide training content and opportunities for users to learn how to use a platform's capabilities, and how to engage with its content and features.
- Use a standardized vocabulary or taxonomy to support better connectivity between content, collaboration between actors and potential for sharing content. An example of an open taxonomy platforms can use is the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy⁴.
- Leverage new technologies; for example, efforts should be made to explore how AI technologies can be used to boost user engagement and avoid any potential negative impacts that such technologies may have.

6.2 Build collaboration and boost interoperability among platforms

Platform operators interviewed expressed an interest in building such connections and in discussing ongoing activities and challenges. Indeed, building coordination and collaborations can support platforms' efforts to deal with budget constraints – by learning from each other, sharing content, and avoiding duplication.

Steps to foster greater collaboration and interoperability include:

- Creating a space for platform managers to share insights with one another, particularly from those managing well established platforms to those with short lifecycles.
- Using a common vocabulary and tagging system to provide clear and easy terms and definitions for users, and to better connect platforms and their data.
- Engaging with platforms that work at different levels (e.g., national and regional).

⁴ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uPh00X7Et_E4Wsp4tqelurVzxPW4gsuEXY136ghXTzc/edit?usp=sharing

6.3 Adopt feasible measures to monitoring impact

Though there are many challenges, the lack of M&E must be overcome to support platforms' development. Moreover, as more platforms develop and mature, it will become increasingly important to engage the intended audience in the planning and development of platforms to ensure their relevance and utility as situations evolve.

Options include:

- Using quick, easy, and accessible feedback mechanisms, such as open feedback forms on a website or a contact email address, to overcome budget constraints on monitoring.
- Using alternative methods, such as webinars and training engagement, to measure capacity development.
- Using and maintaining iterative feedback and co-design processes throughout the lifetime of a platform to ensure that user needs continue to be met.

Quarterly snapshot

Figure 5. Example snapshot of platform progress at quarterly intervals. See Annex 5 for guidance on this MEL approach.

6.4 Continue the Adaptation AGORA community of practice

By building on the webinar series and communications begun under the Adaptation AGORA project, this community can provide a space for platforms to engage, discuss and support one another. Such a group can support efforts to standardize how knowledge is described, managed, and shared between platforms, and improve how information is translated from one context to another.

7. References

- Adam, S., and Weiss, S. Evaluation of the KlimAdapt Project. 2025, p. 10, <https://doi.org/10.60810/OPENUMWELT-7876>.
- Barnard, G., 2011. Seeking a cure for portal proliferation syndrome. *Climate and Development Knowledge Network. Blog*.
- Barrott, J., 2022. Stepping up knowledge exchange between climate adaptation platforms: synthesis report from the KE4CAP project.
- Bharwani, S., Barrott, J., Costello, R., Lokers, R., Foddering, R. (2019). The PLACARD Connectivity Hub: A New 'Search and Discovery' Tool for CCA and DRR. PLACARD Tool
- Bharwani, S., Williamson, K. and Butterfield, R., 2025. Measuring what matters: Building impact pathways to actionable information for the weADAPT platform. *Climate Services*, 38, p.100574.
- Carone, M.T., Antronico, L. and Coscarelli, R., 2025. Learning platforms for climate change adaptation: the importance of effective communication. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), pp.1-10.
- Goonsekera, S.M. and Olazabal, M., 2022. Climate adaptation indicators and metrics: State of local policy practice. *Ecological Indicators*, 145, p.109657.
- Hamill, A., Harvey, B. and Echeverria, D., 2013. Knowledge for action: an analysis of the use of online climate knowledge brokering platforms. *Knowledge Management for Development Journal*, 9(1), pp.72-92.
- Henriksen, D., 2023. Critical platform literacies through a design lens: Technological affordances and the zone of possibilities. *Literacy Learning: The Middle Years*, 31(2), pp.22-25.
- Henriksen, H.J., Roberts, M.J., van der Keur, P., Harjanne, A., Egilson, D. and Alfonso, L., 2018. Participatory early warning and monitoring systems: A Nordic framework for web-based flood risk management. *International journal of disaster risk reduction*, 31, pp.1295-1306.
- Lee, H., Calvin, K., Dasgupta, D., Krinner, G., Mukherji, A., Thorne, P., Trisos, C., Romero, J., Aldunce, P., Barret, K. and Blanco, G., 2023. IPCC, 2023: Climate change 2023: Synthesis report, summary for policymakers. Contribution of working groups I, II and III to the sixth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change [core writing team, h. Lee and j. Romero (eds.)]. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland.
- Lemos, M.C., 2015. Usable climate knowledge for adaptive and co-managed water governance. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 12, pp.48-52.
- Magnan, A.K., 2016. Metrics needed to track adaptation. *Nature*, 530(7589), pp.160-160.

Maibach EW, Uppalapati SS, Orr M, Thaker J (2023) Harnessing the Power of Communication and Behavior Science to Enhance Society's Response to Climate Change. *Annu Rev Earth Planet Sci* 2023 51:53–77

Oliveira, L. and Carvalho, A., 2023. How climate scientists and communication professionals view public engagement with science: Perspectives, practices and constraints. *Frontiers in Communication*, 8, p.1046501.

Panenko, A., George, E. and Lutoff, C., 2021. Towards the development of climate adaptation knowledge-action systems in the European Union: An institutional approach to climate service analysis. *Climate services*, 24, p.100265.

Street, R., Alterio, I., Hewitt, C., Golding, N., New, S. and Mysiak, J., 2022. Enabling climate action: Messages from ECCA2021 calling for re-imagining the provision and use of knowledge and information. *Climate Risk Management*, 36, p.100428.

Swart, R.J., De Bruin, K., Dhenain, S., Dubois, G., Groot, A. and Von Der Forst, E., 2017. Developing climate information portals with users: Promises and pitfalls. *Climate services*, 6, pp.12-22.

Tompkins, E.L., Vincent, K., Nicholls, R.J. and Suckall, N., 2018. Documenting the state of adaptation for the global stocktake of the Paris Agreement. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 9(5), p.e545.

VanderMolen, K., Wall, T.U. and Daudert, B., 2019. A call for the evaluation of web-based climate data and analysis tools. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 100(2), pp.257-268.

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E. and Bouwman, J., 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), pp.1-9.

Annex 1. Survey Questions

Summary

This survey aims to identify information key to strengthening learning and exchange between climate knowledge platforms and build an engaged [community of practice](#) [use the sign-up link to add your platform!] The information gathered will be published in a report and recommendations will be shared at the 2025 European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA).

Key

SO: Select one question; OQ: Open question; MC: Multiple choice question.

Background questions

Consent:

Adhering to GDPR rules, all survey responses are confidential. We collect specific identity details only to help understand the demographic we have reached. The data from this survey will be used for scientific purposes within the Adaptation AGORA project. The analysis of the survey data will be therefore anonymous and aggregated.

Please confirm the following statements* (MC):

- I have read and understood the information provided above.
- I voluntarily consent to participate in this survey.

I consent to the processing of my anonymous data for research purposes* (SO)

- Yes
- No

I consent to follow up for research purposes* (SO)

- Yes
- No

I confirm that I am 18 years or older* (SO)

- Yes
- No

Individual Questions

Number	Question	Answer type	Options
1	Name	OQ	
2	Job role/title	OQ	

3	Are you a platform owner/platform manager?	MC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platform owner - Platform manager - Other (please specify)
4	Sector	SO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research/ Academia - Practitioner - I/NGO - Private - Civil service
5	Gender	SO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Female - Male - Non-binary - Prefer not to say

Platform Questions

Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
9	Name of platform	OQ	
10	Platform website	OQ	
11	What is the name of the host organisation managing/developing the platform	OQ	
12	Please provide the main contact for the platform (name, organisation, role)	OQ	
13	When was the platform launched?	OQ	
14	What is the overarching scope of your platform	OQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation - Disaster risk management - Resilience - Mitigation - Climate data and information - Other (please specify)
15	What are the main goals of the platform?	MC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raising awareness on the need for climate change adaptation

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing guidance on how to undertake adaptation - Providing quantitative data for adaptation decision-making - Providing decision-support tools for adaptation decision-making - Providing a support (e.g. help desk) service - Sharing adaptation solutions and case studies - Sharing scientific literature and research on adaptation - Other (please specify)
13	Who are the intended/targeted audiences for the platform?	MC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National-level decision makers / national government - City and regional-level decision-makers / local government - Communities / general public - Teachers / educators - Private sector / businesses - Research community - Civil society (NGO / charities) - Others (please specify)
14	How do you connect or communicate with your target audience?	OQ	
15	Is the platform focusing on engaging with particular sectors and, if so which ones?	MC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health - Agriculture - Oceans / fisheries - Forests and other ecosystems - Transport - Infrastructure / built environment - Trade

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finance / insurance - Disaster risk - We're not engaging with specific sectors - Other (please specify)
16	What do you consider to be key innovative features of your platform (e.g. unique selling point)	
17	What are the areas you would like to improve in the platform? How do you think this can be achieved?	

M&E and impact questions

Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
19	How do you measure/evaluate the impact of your platform in meeting its scope and goals? E.g. on adaptation, resilience, mitigation or decision-making support	OC	
20	What type of information do you gather on impact?	OC	
21	Can you give examples of the impact your platform has had?	OC	
22	How do you use the information gathered about your platforms impact? E.g. do you incorporate feedback/tailor the platform further; do you share this in newsletter or on social media etc?	OC	
19	Is understanding the impact of your platform useful for knowledge management?	OC	
19a	How do / would you measure the impact of platforms for knowledge management?	OC	

20	How do you think measuring/evaluating the impact of your platform benefits your platform?	OC	
21	Does your online platform aim to help bridge the knowledge-to-action gap?	SO	- Yes - No - Unsure
21a	How does your platform support this?	OC	
22	Does your platform use a theory of change?	SO	- Yes - No - Unsure
22a	Are you able to share a link to your ToC?	OC	
	How do you use the ToC in platform or knowledge management?		
23	What barriers have you faced in achieving your platform's objectives? How can/have these been overcome?	OC	
24	What enablers have supported you in achieving your platforms' objectives?	OC	
25	Does your platform connect/link with any other platforms?	SO	- Yes - No - Unsure
25a	How does your platform connect/link with other platforms?	OC	
26	How does your platform encourage connections and partnerships between users?	OC	
27	Does your platform connect with policy makers, practitioners and/or citizens?	MC	- Policy Makers - Practitioners - Citizens - Other (please specify)
27a	How does the platform connect with policy makers, practitioners and/or citizens?	OC	

27b	How is the information on your platform used by policy makers, practitioners, and/or citizens?	OC
-----	--	----

Adaptation Agora Questions

Number	Question	Answer Type	Answer Options
28	Would you like to feature your platform on the Agora Community Hub platforms page? [link added above]	SO	- Yes - No - Unsure - Its already on there
31	What topics would you like to learn about from other platforms so that we can consider them in our ongoing webinar series [add link]?	OQ	
32	Are you interested in joining the Agora CAPs network to learn from other platforms?	SO	- Yes - No
32a	What would be your preferred form of communication within the CAPs network?	MC	- Agora Community Hub network/discussion forums - LinkedIn - Mailing List
44	Would you like to join our CAPs mailing list/email correspondence?	SO	- Yes - No

Annex 2. Climate Adaptation Platform Interview Questions

General

1. How does your current role relate to climate change adaptation platforms?
 - a. Which platform do you manage/work on?
 - b. What is the aim of your platform?
 - c. Who is the target audience of your platform?
 - d. What is the geographic reach of your platform?
 - e. Is it available in multiple languages?
 - f. How big is the team working on the platform and how is the platform funded?

Section: Are CAPs still useful for adaptation?

2. Do you think CAPs are valuable (in general and for your work)?
3. What could make them more useful (in general and for your work)?
4. How can they support and accelerate adaptation work?
5. What impact is AI having on your work and how could it influence the impact/use/prevalence of CAPs (positively/negatively)?

Section: Coordination and/or collaboration between CAPs

6. Do you think there should better coordination and/or collaboration between CAPs?
 - a. Why/why not?
7. In an ideal world, how do you foresee better coordination and/or collaboration between CAPs?
8. What mechanisms or structures would support this?

Section: Coordination, learning and/or collaboration between users

9. Do you support collaboration/conversation/learning between users? [e.g. subnational regions, COPs]
 - a. If so, how is this achieved?
10. Do you measure the adaptation impact of your platform and if so, how? E.g. analytics or more qualitative measures? What is the most important measure that you use?
 - a. [If no] If you do not measure the adaptation impact of your platform, why not? What are the barriers to doing this?
 - b. [If not covered above] Do you think better evaluation would help your platform and if so how?
 - c. Do you have plans to do this and if so how?
 - d. What support do you need to be able to do this?
11. [If yes] Why do you consider evaluation is important?
 - a. How do you measure/evaluate the impact of your platform in meeting its scope and goals? E.g. on adaptation, resilience, mitigation or decision-making support
 - b. What type of information do you gather on impact?
 - c. Why are these elements important?
12. Can you give examples of the impact your platform has had?
13. How do you use the information gathered about your platforms impact? E.g. do you incorporate feedback/tailor the platform further; do you share this in newsletter or on social media etc?
14. Does your platform use a theory of change?
15. How do you connect or communicate with your target audience?
16. What do you think are the key pathways to action e.g. adaptation action or implementation?

Accessibility

17. How do you make your platform accessible to your audience?

Usability

18. How do you raise awareness of your platform?
19. What type of information is shared on your platform?
20. Does this include grey literature?
21. Do you know how this information is used e.g. the impact it has?
22. Do you consider the information on your platform useable to your target audience?

Inclusivity

23. How does your platform support developing capacity? Both in using the platform and in applying the knowledge. Eg webinars.
 - a. How do you measure the impact of these features?
24. Does your platform offer cross-community learning features enabling users to interact?
 - a. How do you measure the impact of these features?
25. Does your platform aim to include different types knowledge?

Trust

26. How do you develop trust by your users in the content on the platform?
27. Was your platform co-developed? If so, how?
28. How do you receive feedback about your platform?

Transferability

29. How do you ensure that information on your platform is transferrable e.g. across regions, sectors etc.
 - a. How do you measure the impact of these features?

Connectivity

30. How do you connect with content on other platforms?
 - a. How do you measure the impact of these features?
31. How does your platform support building connections between users and knowledge exchange?
 - a. How do you measure the impact of these features?
32. What tagging system do you use on the platform? Is it a standardized approach? Is this something that can be improved or requires support?

Survey

33. You mentioned in the survey that < example >. Could you tell us more about this? Are there specific resources you used?
34. What do you think is missing from how platforms measure their impact?

Annex 3. Pilot Interview Questions

1. What types of citizens/stakeholders do you engage with in your pilot?
2. What type of online platform/information could support your work?
3. How / why is this info on platforms useful?

4. Have you used the ACH in the pilot regions? If so, how?
5. How do or would you like to access information on the ACH [or any online platform that could support your work]? e.g. newsletter, social media, LinkedIn
6. What do the pilots and different stakeholders need from a platform such as the ACH?
7. Do the pilot regions use other climate platforms already? If so, do you know what they are and what do they use them for?
8. What feedback from the pilot regions have you heard about the ACH?
9. How do you think the ACH could be updated to support the pilot regions?
10. How could we build engagement on the ACH from the pilot regions? What would incentivise users?
11. Is there any content from the pilots that you could share with us to include on the ACH?
12. How are you measuring your engagement/evaluation with different groups?

Annex 4. Platforms Interviewed

Interviews were conducted with the following platforms:

1. Climate-ADAPT
2. Climate Adaptation Platform Netherlands
3. German Climate Preparedness Portal (KLiVO-Portal)
4. KE4CAP
5. Mission for Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt)
6. Regions Adapt
7. Spanish Climate Change Adaptation Platform (AdapteCCa)
8. Adaptation Scotland
9. UK Climate Resilience Programme
10. weADAPT

Annex 5. MEL Framework

The monitoring framework below is adapted from the weADAPT platform's MEL approach (Bharwani et al., 2025) and can be adapted further as needed. Some indicators can be gathered through regular software analytics (SA), such as Google or social media analytics data. Others require early integration into platform design for curated analytics (CA), including 'proxy'

indicators that are hard to measure directly and may need indirect measurement and manual effort (M). Additionally, if standardized tags using taxonomies are applied, it becomes easier to collect this data in an automated way (SA-T). Certain indicators are best monitored through mapping and graph visualizations (V). The table below includes columns for baseline, target and trend data, which should be included when using or adapting tables 1-6 to monitor platform impact.

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)	Baseline	Target	Trend
1	Top 10 EU countries accessing the platform (number of users)	SA	European reach	e.g. Baseline: Current engagement rate	e.g. Target: +10% annually	↑ improving

Table 1. Usability

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)
1	Top 10 EU countries accessing the platform (number of users)	SA	European reach
2	Top 10 EU cities accessing the platform (number of users)	SA	European reach at different scales
3	Top 5 EU languages (other than English) website and content is accessed in (where content is translated by the Knowledge Management team)	SA	Tracking availability and uptake of content in multiple EU languages where content is translated manually
4	% of website visits accessed in an EC language other than English (where translation feature is used)	SA	Tracking availability and uptake of content in multiple EU languages where content is translated automatically
5	Feedback mechanisms specific to the platform	CA	Ensuring the platforms are usable e.g. to report to funders
6	Number of page views for platform 'introductory' articles and trainings on climate-related topics	SA	Uptake of training and guidance materials
7	Monitoring page views for key climate hazards in Europe	CA	e.g. heatwaves, floods, droughts, sea-level rise using standardized taxonomy
8	Monitoring page views for key adaptation options in Europe	CA	Using standardized taxonomy e.g. including classification from Climate-ADAPT
9	Monitoring page views for sectors most affected in EU contexts	CA	e.g. agriculture, energy, health, water
10	Measure coverage gaps	CA	e.g. which hazards or sectors are underrepresented
11	Number of new platform users	M	Platform growth
12	Use of feedback forms available and used	SA	Feedback forms available and used
13	Amount of new content, disaggregated by content type	M	E.g. podcast, online seminar, blog, case study

14	Number of times and what type of content is 'bookmarked', saved or downloaded	CA	Uptake of different of 'content types' and popularity, e.g. content is timely and relevant and valued
15	Newsletter download analytics	SA	Readability of syntheses featured in newsletters
16	Diversity of knowledge types (formats) accessed/downloaded	CA	E.g. podcasts, webinars, blogs, case studies
17	Number of new courses added	M	Perception as a place to find good quality learning material
18	EU and national policy document citations	M	Policy uptake

Table 2. Inclusivity

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)
1	Technical inclusivity	SA	Adhering to website accessibility standards e.g. colours, font size, image size, screen use etc.
2	Frequency of inclusion of synonyms and scope notes in taxonomy	CA	Indicative of the platform's aim to support a shared understanding, reveal diverse viewpoints and make explicit different interpretations of terms and concepts. This can also be in the case of language translation.
3	Number of trainings offered on using the platform (disaggregated by gender and role of attendees)	M	Capacity development and technical inclusivity
4	Engagement by stakeholder category (municipalities, regional governments, research institutions, scientists, policymakers, NGOs, SMEs, private sector).	CA	Just, inclusive and equitable access by different actors and knowledge types
5	Contribution by stakeholder category (municipalities, regional governments, research institutions, scientists, policymakers, NGOs, SMEs, private sector).	CA	Just, inclusive and equitable contributions by different knowledge types
6	Number of local, youth or marginalized groups and organizations e.g. rural accessing content	M	Just, inclusive and equitable access by different actor types
7	Number of new published content authored by local, youth or marginalized groups and organizations e.g. rural	M	Just, inclusive and equitable representation of different knowledge types
8	Disciplinary diversity of Editors	M	e.g. transdisciplinary
9	Diversity of range of thematic content	M	e.g. practical and policy related vs academic
10	% of content that is relevant to policy makers and practitioners (rather than academic): Diversity of knowledge types by theme	CA	e.g. operationalized example to learn from other regions
11	Number of times and what type of content is 'bookmarked', saved or downloaded	CA	Uptake of different of 'content types' and popularity, e.g. content is timely and relevant and valued

12	Top 5 EU languages (other than English) website and content is accessed in (where content is translated manually)	SA	Tracking availability and uptake of content in multiple EU languages (where content is translated manually)
13	% of website visits accessed in an EC language other than English (where translation feature is used)	SA	Tracking availability and uptake of content in multiple EU languages (where content is translated automatically)
14	Diversity of knowledge types (formats)	CA	E.g. podcasts, webinars, blogs, case studies
15	How often the newsletter is downloaded (e.g. so that it can be printed or read later)	SA	Supporting equity of knowledge sharing and access
16	Diversity in who is creating and defining new taxonomy terms and synonyms	CA	Indigenous and other minority groups are involved in the development of content, terms, synonyms and definitions. Just and equal representation of all knowledge types, viewpoints and interpretations of information

Table 3. Trust

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)
1	Analytics of featured downloads by geography, institute/affiliation and professional role of contributor	M	Quality and breadth of resources shared
2	Citation analytics	SA	Trusted source
3	Contributors changing status from subscriber and platform browser to avid readers, Editors or Champions (e.g. if badges or incentives are included on the platform)	CA	Increasing engagement and recognition of added value of engaging with the platform
4	Newsletter reads and how often the newsletter is shared through social media, opened, clicked on or forwarded	CA	Indicative of a trusted source that can be publicly shared with contacts and networks, multiplier effect
5	How often the newsletter is downloaded (e.g. so that it can be printed or read later)	SA	Indicative of a trusted source that can be publicly shared with peers or community members
6	Number of times and what type of content is 'bookmarked', saved or downloaded	CA	Uptake of different of 'content types' and popularity, e.g. content is timely and relevant and valued
7	How much content Editors work with and to what degree they or the Knowledge Manager engage with contributors.	M	Depth of co-production process
8	Analytics of featured downloads by number of saves, geography, institute/affiliation and professional role of contributor	M	Diversity and spread of content type and source accessing it. Assumption that this is done based on credibility and trust
9	Use of standardized forms or approaches	SA	To encourage user feedback. Responsiveness can help build trust.

Table 4. Place-based knowledge sharing

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)
1	% of national and regional case studies that relate to EU adaptation priorities	SA -T	Diversity of adaptation priorities represented
2	% of national and regional case studies that relate to EU adaptation sectoral policies	SA-T	Diversity of sectors represented in content shared
3	Number of national and regional case studies covering key European risks, hazards and climate impacts (including transboundary)	SA-T	Diversity of risks, hazards and impacts represented in content shared (including transboundary)
4	Number of resources linked to EU Climate-ADAPT knowledge base.	M	Visibility at European level
5	Spatial scale of content shared: Case studies disaggregated by sub-national units (e.g. regional, basin, city etc.)	SA-T	Diversity of scales represented in content shared
6	Number of case studies contributed from different European countries and from transboundary regions	SA	Breadth of contributions - including cross-border engagement (e.g., number of users contributing content from more than one European country).
7	Number of times case studies are viewed by different European countries	SA	Depth and richness of engagement (e.g., number of users accessing content from more than one European country).
8	Average session time for case studies	SA	Depth and richness of engagement
9	Number of times and what type of case studies are 'bookmarked', saved or downloaded	CA	Uptake of different of 'content types' and popularity, e.g. content is timely and relevant and valued
10	Diversity of geographical location of contributions	SA-T, V	Landscape diversity of the platform, e.g. small islands, Alpine, coasts, etc
11	Analytics of featured downloads by number of saves, geography, institute/affiliation and professional role of contributor	M	Diversity and spread of content type and source accessing it.

Table 5. Connectivity and cross-fertilization between knowledge, users, and networks

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)
1	How much content different organizations share	CA, V	Active organizations
2	How many different topic areas organizations contribute to	CA, V	Activity and potential for cross-fertilization if organizations are contributing to multiple themes
3	Most frequent topics (tags) content (e.g. projects, organizations) is connected to	SA-T, V	Connectivity and cross-fertilization across the knowledge and network landscape. Can potentially reveal gaps in the knowledge and network landscape
4	Number of times content items (articles, case etc) are linked to different topic areas	CA, V	Connectivity and cross-fertilization. An indicator of how much knowledge is connected.

5	Number of followers an individual/organization has or how many individuals/organizations they follow	CA, V	Connectivity between organizations
6	Number of times organizations are visited	SA	Connectivity, popularity and relevance of the work of the organization
7	Number of 'messages' sent between members	CA	Connectivity between members
8	How frequently social media channels are re-sharing platform content and any engagement analytics, such as likes, shares and comments	SA	Connectivity and cross-fertilization. May imply sharing of content through professional networks also.
9	Number and type of referrals (e.g. top 10 sources of traffic to the platform)	SA	Connectivity and popularity of the platform
10	Number of new comments	SA	Depth of interactivity
11	Number of new forum posts	SA	Depth of interactivity
12	Referrals from other national adaptation portals or networks	SA	Key measure of connectivity
13	Number of communities of practice around a topic or issue formed through the platform	M	Connectivity and cross-fertilization across the knowledge and network landscape.
14	Engagement via online contributions or attendance rate at core events	M	Connectivity and cross-fertilization across the knowledge and network landscape.
15	Transboundary, cross-national and regional collaborations initiated	M	Transboundary connectivity and cross-fertilization across the knowledge and network landscape.
16	Cross-border uptake of nationally produced resources	M	Transboundary relevance of resources
17	Cooperation with neighbouring countries on adaptation (joint workshops, shared datasets)	M	Regional collaboration

Table 6. FAIR Knowledge Management

#	Example indicator	How this is captured	Notes on types of impact (direct and proxy indicators)
1	How much links to 'related content' are used	CA	
2	Use of translation feature and top 5 languages (other than English) website is accessed in	SA	Diversity of languages used and value of manual translation compared to the translation feature
3	How much low energy elements of the site are used	CA	Effectiveness in increasing accessibility in low bandwidth areas
4	Analytics of featured downloads by number of saves, geography, institute/affiliation and professional role of contributor	M, V	A possible indicator that content is downloaded to read offline.
5	How often the newsletter is downloaded (so that it can be printed or read later)	SA	Indicative of accessibility of resource

6	Use of a taxonomy	SA-T	Supporting a shared understanding, diverse viewpoints and making explicit different interpretations of terms and concepts. Particularly in the case of technical language.
7	How many times and which words are hovered over (e.g. to access definitions, synonyms etc.)	CA	Which terms users require clarity on or definitions.
8	Number of new taxonomy terms and synonyms created and defined	CA, V	Ensuring connectivity across content both within and across platforms.
9	Top 10 most used tags	SA-T	Can inform ways to increase interoperability across key topic areas (tags)
10	What tags most contributor content connects to	V	To identify expertise, interests and geographies
11	Use of APIs	SA	To encourage connections between platform content and data sharing

